

Adducts of Nickel(II) with Salicylaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone and Monodentate Ligands

(Miss) MINATI BARAL, B. K. KANUNGO and B. PRADHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

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A series of complexes of the type $Ni(stsc)L$, where $L = \gamma$ -picoline, isoquinoline, pyridine-*N*-oxide, thiourea, imidazole, and triphenylphosphine, have been isolated by the reaction of nickel(II) salt and the ligands in stoichiometric ratio. The compounds characterised on the basis of analytical, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data and molecular weight measurements were found to be distorted tetrahedral. Some of them indicate the probability of being associated with a tetrahedral \rightleftharpoons square-planar isomerism.

NICKEL(II) forms a large number of complexes encompassing coordination numbers 4, 5 and 6.

Among the four coordinated complexes following stoichiometric types, NiX_2^- , NiX_3L^- , NiX_2L_2 and $Ni(L-L)_2$, where X represents a uninegative ligand; L, a neutral ligand; and (L-L), one of the several types of bidentate ligands, are known. However, complexes of nickel(II) of the type $Ni(L'-L''-L''')L$ with tridentate ligands ($L'-L''-L'''$) are very rare. Tetrahedral complexes of divalent nickel containing sulphur-bonded ligands are not known. Thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones are known to be used as various life saving drugs¹⁻³. Some drugs were found to have increased activity when administered as metal complexes^{4,5}. Since Mashima's work⁶, coordination chemists have shown enough interest in thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones. The complexing ability of thiosemicarbazones has been reported earlier from this laboratory^{7,8}. In the present communication, an attempt has been made to investigate the nature and preference of divalent nickel ion when provided with a binegative tridentate chelate alongwith nitrogen, oxygen, sulphur or phosphorous donor neutral ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The thiosemicarbazones were prepared by the method adopted by Beecroft *et al.*⁹. Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoxime¹⁰. The ir spectra (4000-400 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra (340-900 nm) were recorded on a Elico CL-24 spectrophotometer using acetone as solvent. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by a Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated by using Pascal's constants¹¹. The

conductance measurements were carried out in $\sim 10^{-3} M$ acetone solution using a Systronics 303 direct reading conductivity meter. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by Rast's method using biphenyl as solvent. The relevant analytical and physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1, and ir and electronic spectral data in Table 2.

Preparation of complexes: To an ethanolic solution of $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, a solution of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in hot acetone and ethanol (1:1, v/v) was added followed by isoquinoline/ γ -picoline/pyridine-*N*-oxide/imidazole/thiourea/triphenylphosphine in equimolecular ratio. The resultant solution was stirred vigorously and a very dilute solution of ammonia was added dropwise till the complexes separated out, which were then suction-filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed with ethanol, ether and dried under vacuum.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are fairly soluble in acetone. The very low values of molar conductance (Table 1) indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes.

Analyses of nickel and sulphur by standard methods suggested the composition of the compounds to be $[Ni(stsc)L]$, where stsc is salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and L is γ -picoline (γ -pic)/pyridine-*N*-oxide (pyNo)/isoquinoline (iq)/thiourea (tu)/imidazole (iz)/triphenylphosphine (ph₃p). All the compounds except $[Ni(stsc)iq]$ are dark coloured. The molecular weight measurement indicates that the compounds are monomeric in nature. For tetracoordinated complexes, two stereochemistries *i.e.* paramagnetic tetrahedral one with two unpaired electrons (3T_1 ground state with T_d symmetry) and diamagnetic square-planar complexes with no unpaired electrons ($^1A_{1g}$ ground state¹ with D_{4h}

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Ni% : Found/(Calcd.)	Ω^{-1} Λ_M $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
1.	Ni(stsc)(iz)	Brick red	160	18.0 (18.3)	1.9	3.53
2.	Ni(etso)(tu)	Pale orange	>250	17.5 (17.9)	3.0	3.10
3.	Ni(stso)(pyNo)	Yellow	>250	17.8 (16.9)	3.2	2.84
4.	Ni(etso)(γ -pic)	Maroon	190	17.0 (17.0)	1.6	1.74
5.	Ni(stso)(iq)	Brown	225	15.8 (15.4)	2.0	1.57
6.	Ni(stso)(pph ₃ P)	Maroon	215	11.7 (11.8)	1.8	1.82

 TABLE 2—INFRARED (cm^{-1}) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA (nm) OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	ν_s ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$	ν_s ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3A_2(F)$	Stsc			
				$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{C-S}	
1.	Ni(stso)(iz)	540	840	—	1 600, 1 470	1 920	665
2.	Ni(stso)(tu)	540	840	—	1 600, 1 470	1 920	650
3.	Ni(stso)(pyNo)	560	840	—	1 600, 1 470	1 945	650
4.	Ni(stso)(γ -pic)	540	860	420 w	1 600, 1 440	1 910	600
5.	Ni(stso)(iq)	560	850	480 w	1 600, 1 410	1 920	650
6.	Ni(stso)(pph ₃ P)	540	860	440 w	1 600, 1 470	1 915	610

ν_{max} : iz, 1 450(NH), tu, 1 450, 1 100, 760(C-S), PyNo, 1 210(N-O) 855(δ N-O), 760(C-H); γ -pic, 1 600(C=C) + 1 520(C=N), iq, 1 600(C-O) + 1 540(C-N); pph₃, 1 480, 1 440, 1 095 cm^{-1} .

symmetry), are known. Fairly regular tetrahedral complexes show magnetic moment of 3.5–4.0 B.M. while for distorted one the values are 3.0–3.5 B.M.¹². It has been reported that for ligand fields depart from tetrahedral symmetry or incase of electron delocalisation, the moments tend to be closer to the spin-only value (2.83 B.M.) and vary less with temperature¹³. Only one complex from the series, viz. Ni(stsc)iz exhibited normal magnetic moment (3.5 B.M.) as expected for a regular tetrahedral one. In the complexes containing thiourea and pyridine-*N*-oxide, the μ_{eff} value approached to the spin-only value (Table 1) which indicate that the system experienced either distortion or electron delocalisation. Other three complexes containing γ -picoline, isoquinoline and triphenyl-phosphine exhibited magnetic moment values in the range 1.57–1.82 B.M. which suggest the presence of a tetrahedral-square-planar isomerism in these compounds. Similar observations have also been reported for some substituted phosphine complexes¹⁴.

Infrared spectra: Salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone behaves as a dibasic tridentate ligand. Deprotonation of phenolic-OH and coordination through oxygen is indicated by the occurrence of $\nu_{C=O}$ at 1 315–1 345 cm^{-1} (Table 2). A sharp band at 1 600 cm^{-1} (C=N) of the Schiff base indicate the coordination of the chelate through azomethine nitrogen. The Schiff base has undergone keto-thioenol tautomerism in alkaline medium and

subsequent coordination to the metal ion by deprotonation of C-SH group is indicated by the absence of bands in the region 2 800–2 650 cm^{-1} ¹⁵. This is further supported by a new band appearing at \sim 650 cm^{-1} ^{16,17}. An additional band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ (found by thioenolisation of the Schiff base) appearing at 1 470 cm^{-1} confirms the thioenol coordination of the ligand. Hence it is conclusive that the ligand salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone is coordinated as a binategative tridentate (O, N and S) ligand. One of the bands of $\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=N}$ at 1 600 cm^{-1} due to γ -picoline and isoquinoline is found to overlap with the band of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, whereas the other one was found at \sim 1 540 cm^{-1} . This suggests the coordination of these ligands through the nitrogen atom¹⁸. The bonding of N-oxide ligands to the metal ion is usually discussed from its bands due to ν_{N-O} , δ_{N-O} and ν_{C-H} in the free state and on complexation. The ν_{N-O} of pyridine-*N*-oxide occurs at 1 265 cm^{-1} but undergoes a marked shift when it is bonded to the metal through oxygen atom. The δ_{N-O} and ν_{C-H} will undergo either positive or negative shift or occur at the same region, 850 and 740 cm^{-1} , respectively. The ν_{N-O} in the complex under report (Table 2) is found at 1 210 cm^{-1} . The shifting of the band from 1 265 cm^{-1} in the free ligand to the lower frequency can be attributed to a change in the N-O bond order as a result of coordination of the ligand through its oxygen atom^{19,20}. In case of the complex containing triphenyl phosphine, strong and sharp bands are

observed at 1 480, 1 440 and 1 095 cm^{-1} , indicating the presence of coordinated ligand in the compound²¹.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectral bands with their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. In T_d symmetry, Ni^{II} (d^8 -configuration) gives rise to a ${}^3T_1(F)$ ground state. Transition from this state to the ${}^3T_1(P)$ state (ν_3) occurs in the visible region (~ 660 nm)²², but for low symmetry T_d complexes the band is observed at 500–660 nm. Besides, bands are also occur at 840–1 000 nm and ~ 1 111 nm due to $\nu_2({}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3A_2(F))$ transitions²³. In the present case, three adducts containing pyridine-*N*-oxide, thiourea and imidazole exhibit characteristic bands at 540–560 nm and 840 nm due to ν_3 and ν_2 transitions, respectively, which support the T_d symmetry for the complexes. No absorption due to ν_1 is observed. Weaker bands in the spectrum are obtained due to spin-forbidden transitions. The square-planar complexes show bands at 400 and 600 nm²⁴. In the present investigation three compounds, viz. $\text{Ni}(\text{stsc})(\text{iq})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{stsc})(\gamma\text{-pic})$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{stsc})(\text{ph}_3\text{p})$ exhibit bands at ~ 400 nm in addition to the bands due to tetrahedral complexes. This indicates the possible presence of tetrahedral \rightleftharpoons square-planar isomerism in the complexes.

Thus, through this communication a series of four-coordinated novel compounds of divalent nickel containing one bidentate tridentate ligand with O, N, S donor sites and a neutral monodentate N, O, S or P donor ligand is reported. Interestingly, the same four-coordinated compounds were obtained even on reacting with excess neutral ligands.

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